

A Study on Consumer Buying Behaviour in Choosing Personal Care Products Based on Financial Status

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Abstract

This research study is basically to find out the consumer behaviour in selecting the personal care products for their own use. This research has been done to find out the consumer behaviour of how they buy the products in the market place because the consumer is the king of the market. we can say that the wide range of products and service can make out Indian economy stronger. but in our market, there are huge number of products are available and it is very difficult for the consumer to choose the products according to their need and also to take a decision to buy the product. This study mainly focuses on to find the impact of variable selection of the personal care products and also to find the how the consumer taking the financial decision to buy the personal care products. Particularly this study shows the market variables influence the buying behaviour of the consumer and also the financial status of the consumer for buying of personal care products.

Key Words: Consumer Behaviour, Personal Care Products, Buying Decision, Financial Status.

Introduction

Consumer is the king because consumer knows everything. especially this study mainly focuses on the buying behaviour of the personal care products for their own use. basically, if the products demand and supply is increase in the market, we can say that the usage of the product is increasing. This study is to find out the consumer behaviour and factors influencing the consumers to making a buying decision because the consumer plays the important roles in the market place. In market the consumer plays the different role for starting to ending for taking a decision to buy the products. a consumer behaviour we can't say that why the consumer is buying the product, and what the consumer can think about the product while taking a decision to buy the product and also, we don't know what market influence the consumer to buy the product like brand, colour etc. this research has done to know about the consumer behaviour for buying a product.

Objectives of the study

1. To Know the concept of consumer behaviour towards purchase of personal care products.
2. To identify the factors influencing consumer behaviour in selection of personal care products.
3. To analyses the importance of the financial status of the consumers in selection of the personal care products.

Review of literature

Sonam Kulkarni Jaiswal (2021) The researcher says that annual family income does not have a significant effect on consumer innovativeness regarding body care products in the Indore region. This suggests that people of all income levels are equally open to trying out new types of body care products.

Md Salim Hossain and Nasrin Sultana Shila (2020) in their study they identified that consumers, especially female consumers are more concerned about specialized products, so while promoting a product marketers can focus on how the product is especially made for women or how it is made for specific type of skin or hair which will attract more consumers.

Anantha Kumar S (2017) in this study it highlighted the importance of a company's ability to attract and retain customers in the personal care products industry. If strong brand image equips companies with effective competitive advantages against rivals in the market. Before devising and implementing their marketing strategies, organizations should consider factors such as product quality, promotional offers, competitive pricing, social status, and after-sales service. Companies should focus on factors that drive consumer purchases, such as low prices, warranty periods, festival offers, discounts, product variety, and product availability.

Anu jose (2016) this study shows that today's ecological problems are severe, that corporations do not act responsibly toward the environment and that behaving in an ecologically favourable fashion is important and not inconvenient.

Scope of the study

This research mainly helps to understand the consumer buying behaviour on selecting the personal care products and also, to know how the financial status influences the consumer which making decision for purchasing the product.

Data collection

The primary Data collect was made through online Google form around 125 respondents were collected .Both the primary and secondary data were collected for this study. Data has been collected from various secondary sources like journals, newspapers, Books, websites, conferences etc.

Factors Influence the Consumer

Consumer behaviour is influenced by several factors such as internal or psychological factors, social factors, cultural factors, economic factors, and personal factors. In this study, all these factors are considered to analyze their impact on the selection of personal care products. Psychological factors relate to the internal feelings and motivations of a person that encourage them to purchase a particular product. Social factors influence consumer behaviour through the social status and relationships of individuals. Cultural factors also play an important role, as people often choose products based on their cultural values and traditions. Economic factors are essential because the financial condition of consumers affects their purchasing decisions. In addition to these factors, personal factors such as age, lifestyle, and preferences play a significant role in the decision-making process.

Data analysis and Interpretation

Table No: 1

Demographic details of the respondents

Demographic factors	Classifications	No of respondents	Percentage
Age	Less than 25 years	13	10.4
	26 to 35 years	36	28.4
	36 to 45 years	60	47.8
	More than 45 years	16	13.4
	Total	125	100.0
Gender	Male	21	16.4
	Female	104	83.6
	Total	125	100.0
Monthly Income	Less than Rs.15,000	41	32.8
	Rs.15,001 to Rs.25,000	49	38.8
	Rs.25,001 to Rs.35,000	13	10.4
	More than Rs.35,000	22	17.9
	Total	125	100.0
Family type	Nuclear	69	55.2
	Joint family	56	44.8
	Total	125	100.0
Marital status	Married	103	82.1
	Unmarried	22	17.9
	Total	125	100.0
Occupation	Public sector	34	26.9
	Private sector	54	43.3
	Business	11	9.0
	Unemployed	26	20.9
	Total	125	100.0
Educational qualification	UG	24	19.4

	PG	67	53.7
	Professional	34	26.9
	Total	125	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that data were collected from 125 respondents. Majority (47.8%) of the respondents come under the age group of 36 to 45 years. Around 83.6% of the respondents are female. Under the monthly income category majority (38.8%) of the respondents come under Rs.15, 001 to Rs.25, 000. When compared to joint family nuclear family respondents are more (55.2%) in this study. Among the respondents majority (82.1%) of them are married. Most (43.3%) of the respondents are working in the private sector. Most of the respondents (36%) are post graduates. Gender and branded products

In this study we collected the data from the consumers based on the gender is recorded. The view of the consumer of both the male and female regarding branded products was collected.

Consumer buying behaviour in selection of personal care products

The buying behaviour of the consumers will be influenced by various factors while making the buying decision. Here the preferences of the consumers are ranked to understand their behaviour in selection of personal care products.

Table No: 4
Consumer behaviour in selection of personal care products

S.No	Consumer Behaviour	Mean	Rank
1	The products which suits to my personality	4.19	1
2	Financial Status decides my personal products	4.15	2
3	I gather information before making buying decision	3.96	3
4	I buy only branded products	3.94	4
5	I give preference to the herbal based products	3.84	5
6	If Media influencing me to buy different types of product	3.52	6
7	Importance given to the products available in discount	3.48	7
8	I collect others opinion before making the purchase decision	3.39	8
9	My status decided through using of personal care products	3.12	9

The above mean table explains the preferences of consumers in selecting personal care products. Consumers give the more importance to buying products that suit their personality. The second important factor influencing their selection is their status of financial position. Consumers also gather information about products before making a purchase decision. Although so many products are available in the market, they prefer only branded products. Media also plays an major role in influencing their choice of personal care products. At the same time, consumers pay focus to products that are available at discounted prices. They also consider peoples' opinions regarding the performance of the product before purchasing personal care items. However, consumers feel that personal care products are not very much important in determining a person's current social status.

Conclusion

This particular study was concluded in to that there are various factors influencing the buyers behaviour in selection of the personal care products for their personal use and for their family use. They are giving priority to products which suits their personality and financial position is also playing a very important role in selecting the personal care products. The study was further conclude into that financial status of the consumers plays a vital role in selection of personal care products for their own use and their family members use. Those who are earning more are spending more for their personal care products and those who are earning less are spending only reasonable amount for their personal care products.